

14. KONGRES FARMAKOLOGA I
4. KONGRES KLINIČKE
FARMAKOLOGIJE SRBIJE
sa međunarodnim učešćem

14th SERBIAN CONGRESS OF
FARMACOLOGISTS AND
4th SERBIAN CONGRESS OF
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⁵ Clinic for nephrology, Clinical center Niš

⁶ Department for pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Niš

⁷ Department for anatomy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Niš

⁸ Faculty of Medicine, University of Niš

The treatment of advanced cervical cancer implies cisplatin chemotherapy. Cytological morphometric parameters of pathohistological preparations of cancer tissue can be useful in the prediction of the therapeutic response - survival in these patients. The aim of this study was to determine the correlation of cell morphometric tissue parameters of advanced cervical cancer - cell surface and cell perimeter with pharmacotherapeutic response to cisplatin chemotherapy.

This study is a prospective study involving 59 patients with advanced cervical cancer treated at the Clinic for oncology Clinical Center Niš. All patients received, with adequate premedication, the same cytostatic - cisplatin at a dose of 40 mg/m² in six therapeutic cycles once a week. Photo documentation was made by photographing the product using the Leica DFC295 digital camera. The morphometric analysis carried out in this study was done using a software package for analyzing and processing digital photographs ImageJ version 1.50.

It has been shown that statistically significant higher cell surface and cell perimeter of the cells had patients with the longest survival time (longer than 12 months) compared to patients who had survival shorter than 6 months for $p < 0.001$, but compared to patients who had survival between 6 and 12 months, for $p < 0.05$. Both morphometric features of the cells, cell surface and cell perimeter, increased with the length of survival of the patients.

The cell surface and cell perimeter can be considered as useful parameters in the prediction of the pharmacotherapeutic response to cisplatin chemotherapy in advanced cervical cancer.

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PATOHISTOLOŠKE PROMENE EKSPERIMENTALNIH FIBROSARKOMA KOD HRČAKA TRETIRANIH METFORMINOM I NITROGLICERINOM

Dušica J. Popović¹, Kosta J. Popović², Dejan Miljković¹, Jovan K. Popović^{3}, Dušan Lalošević¹, Ivan Čapo¹*

¹Zavod za histologiju i embriologiju, Medicinski fakultet, Univerzitet u Novom Sadu, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21137 Novi Sad, Republika Srbija

²Zavod za farmaciju, Medicinski fakultet, Univerzitet u Novom Sadu, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21137 Novi Sad, Republika Srbija

^{3*} Zavod za farmakologiju, toksikologiju i kliničku farmakologiju, Medicinski fakultet, Univerzitet u Novom Sadu, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21137 Novi Sad, Republika Srbija

Ispitivani su ankancerski efekti metformina i nitroglicerina. Imunohistohemija eksperimentalnih tumora fibrosarkoma ispitivana je kod hrčaka tretiranih metforminom i nitroglicerinom. Hrčkovima su injicirane BHK-21/C13 ćelije da bi se indukovao fibrosarkom, i životinje su tretirane svakodnevno metforminom, nitroglicerinom ili kombinacijom ova dva leka. Nakon toga su prikupljeni uzorci krvi za biohemijske analize, a tumori su ekscidirani. Uzorci tumora su patohistološki i imunohistokemijski analizirani za proliferacioni protein marker Ki-67, endotelni indikator angiogeneze CD34, mitohondrijalni marker koji koristi citohrom oksidazu subjedinicu 4 (COX4), transporter glukoze 1 (GLUT1) i citoplazmatski indikator izraženosti enzima inducibilne NO (azot monoksid) sintetaze (iNOS), a vitalni organi su toksikološki analizirani. U uzorcima tumora kvantifikovana je Ki-67-pozitivnost i imunoekspresija citoplazmatskih markera (CD34, COX4, GLUT1, iNOS).

Rezultati su pokazali da kombinacija metformina i nitroglicerina značajno menja patohistološke karakteristike fibrosarkoma hrčaka, uključujući Ki-67-pozitivnost i imunoekspresiju citoplazmatskih markera, bez indikacija toksičnosti. Primena metformina u kombinaciji sa nitroglicerinom inhibira proliferaciju fibrosarkoma *in vivo*, što ukazuje da ova kombinacija može biti kandidat za novu efikasnu, sigurnu i netoksičnu antikancersku adjuvantnu terapiju ili terapiju prevencije relapsa.

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PATHOHISTOLOGICAL CHANGES IN EXPERIMENTAL FIBROSARCOMA TUMORS OF HAMSTERS TREATED WITH METFORMIN AND NITROGLYCERIN

Dušica J. Popović¹, Kosta J. Popović², Dejan Miljković¹, Jovan K. Popović^{3}, Dušan Lalošević¹, Ivan Čapo¹*

¹Department of Histology and Embriology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21137 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

²Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21137 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

^{3*}Department of Pharmacology, Toxicology and Clinical Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21137 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

The anticancer effects of metformin and nitroglycerin were investigated. The immunohistochemistry of experimental fibrosarcoma tumors was investigated in hamsters treated with metformin and nitroglycerin. The hamsters were injected with BHK-21/C13 cells in order to induce fibrosarcoma, and the animals were treated daily with metformin, nitroglycerin or a combination of the two drugs. Subsequently, blood samples were obtained for biochemical analyses and the tumors were excised. The tumor samples were pathohistologically and immunohistochemically assessed for proliferation marker protein Ki-67, hematopoietic progenitor cell antigen CD34, cytochrome *c* oxidase subunit 4 (COX4), glucose transporter 1 (GLUT1) and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), and vital organs were toxicologically tested. Ki-67-positivity and cytoplasmic marker (CD34, COX4, GLUT1, iNOS) immunoexpression in the tumor samples were quantified. The results revealed that the combination of metformin and nitroglycerin significantly altered the pathohistological characteristics of the hamster fibrosarcoma tumors, including Ki-67-positivity and the immunoexpression of cytoplasmic markers, without indications of toxicity. In conclusion, the administration of metformin in combination with nitroglycerin may inhibit fibrosarcoma proliferation *in vivo*, suggesting that this may be an effective and safe approach as a nontoxic anticancer adjuvant and relapse prevention therapy.

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FIZIČKO-HEMIJSKE PROMENE EKSPERIMENTALNIH FIBROSARKOMA KOD HRČAKA TRETIRAANIH METFORMINOM I NITROGLICERINOM